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ABSTRACT

The present work experimentally examines the aeroacoustic characteristics of a propeller ingesting various planar turbulent boundary layers. The experimental setup consists of a two-bladed propeller, operating at a constant advance ratio, positioned close to a flat plate in the boundary layer ingestion configuration (BLI) with a fixed propeller-plate clearance. To investigate the sensitivities of the far-field noise signature of the BLI configuration to the inflow conditions, three incoming turbulent boundary layers of varying thicknesses and turbulence energy contents were developed. The resulting far-field acoustics and near-field velocity were captured using microphone arrays and hot-wire anemometry. Far-field acoustic results show that increasing the boundary layer thickness, and turbulence contents, sees a significant rise of the broadband components in the mid-frequencies, with strong directivity, a useful property to manipulate during aircraft design. Upstream flow field results confirm that the presence of the propeller induces a mild elevation in both the velocity and its fluctuations within the boundary layers, with the highest increase associated with the thickest boundary layer. Additionally, to understand the distinct acoustic and flow behavior over a revolution of the propeller, i.e., when the propeller is moving in and out of the boundary layer, phase-averaging of the acoustic and velocity signals was performed. The phase-averaged results showed strong pulsation in the steady and unsteady velocities around the propeller and also identified that the peak of the broadband noise generation occurs when the propeller is close to perpendicular to the plate and during peak local velocity perturbation.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The necessity of reducing the environmental impact of civil aviation, as a consequence of its exponential growth, has led researchers and aircraft manufacturers to take a closer look at advanced and innovative aircraft configurations which have the potential to effectively reduce fuel consumption and improve efficiency. A current popular configuration involves the placement of the propulsor in very close proximity to the fuselage to partially, or totally, ingest the incoming airframe boundary layer. This configuration is called boundary layer ingestion (BLI) and is an unconventional airframe-propulsion integration architecture that is featured on several future-flight aircraft concepts with the aim of reducing the overall aircraft energy consumption.¹

As the propulsor ingests and accelerates the reduced flow velocity of the fuselage boundary layer, it consumes less energy in the process than if it were to take in the pure freestream, recovering some of the

losses due to viscous drag.^{2–4} The seminal work of Smith and Roberts⁵ first highlighted the potential benefits of a BLI configuration. By drawing the airframe boundary layer through the fuselage and into a propulsor, they found that drag was reduced and flight range was increased. Subsequently, Douglass⁶ analyzed the performance of the BLI design, underlining a fuel saving of up to 16% when compared to a non-BLI counterpart. Later, Smith⁷ provided an in-depth investigation of a propeller ingesting an axisymmetric wake, an alternative to a fuselage-mounted configuration. Using an incompressible, inviscid actuator disk analysis, he found that a 7% power saving was realizable if the entire wake was ingested. Uranga *et al.*⁸ investigated the benefits of BLI for the D8 aircraft. The experimental campaign involved both a BLI and a non-BLI 1:11 scale model being tested in the NASA Langley wind tunnel. The results showed an 8.6% power benefit for the BLI case under cruise conditions. More recently, there have been studies

on various implementations of BLI with reports of substantial power savings being possible.^{9,10}

Despite a number of studies on the potential performance improvements of the BLI configuration, the acoustic consequences were less well studied and understood. Naturally, ingesting a boundary layer that is significantly more turbulent than the freestream flow would lead to an increase in turbulence interaction noise. As an increase in propulsion noise is undesirable, particularly in an urban setting,^{11,12} it is essential to investigate and understand the nature of the noise emitted from the BLI integration and develop methods for prediction. Earlier work on turbulence interaction noise considered a propeller as a set of isolated airfoils and attempted to model the noise from each blade using strip theory, from which the noise generated by the entire propeller could be calculated.¹³ However, the approach neglected important blade-to-blade correlation effects. In the later studies by Sevik¹⁴ and Hanson,¹⁵ they considered a rotor ingesting isotropic and anisotropic turbulence, respectively, and observed significant broadband humps in the acoustic spectra due to the turbulence interaction. Moreover, for highly stretched, anisotropic turbulence, the broadband humps narrowed, resembling the tones of the rotor harmonics. Sevik¹⁴ showed that the broadband hump could be partly captured when the spanwise correlation length of the turbulence impinging on the blade was accounted for in the strip theory. Subsequently, Wojno *et al.*¹⁶ carried out an experiment on the turbulence interaction with a rotor, similar to that of Sevik. By fully characterizing the three-dimensional length scale of the incoming turbulence, they demonstrated that relatively accurate prediction of the broadband levels could be achieved, suggesting that detailed knowledge of the velocity fields was necessary to model the turbulence interaction noise. Since then, there have been more studies investigating the noise characteristics of a propeller interacting with turbulence of different scales using analytical,^{17,18} numerical,¹⁹ and experimental²⁰ tools, to name a few.

Stephen and Morris²¹ extended Sevik's study by considering a rotor interacting with the turbulent boundary layer from a duct, i.e., a ducted version of the Sevik rotor. Two-point velocity measurements were performed to provide spatiotemporal correlation of the inflow turbulence and they confirmed that the semiempirical prediction based on the velocity fields agreed well with the experimental noise measurements for the first five blade passing frequency (BPF) tones. Glegg *et al.*²² showed that the noise from a near-wall rotor, ingesting anisotropic and inhomogeneous turbulence, could be predicted by a time domain approach for moderate thrust conditions as long as the inflow turbulence was completely characterized, which further corroborated earlier studies, such as in Refs. 16 and 21. However, this approach could not be applied to high-thrust conditions. Subsequently, Murray *et al.*²³ experimentally studied a rotor partially immersed in a planar turbulent boundary layer at a low Mach number. They found that the rotor produced broadband noise with haystacking characteristics, generated by large eddies of the ingested turbulence being cut multiple times by successive rotor blades. Moreover, at high thrust, the acoustic signature became louder and more tonal. This change was accompanied by the separation of the boundary layer from the wall in the vicinity of the rotor blade disk.

More recently, Hickling²⁴ conducted an extensive experimental campaign to look at two configurations, a propeller ingesting a turbulent wake from an upstream cylinder, and a propeller ingesting a turbulent boundary layer at the rear of an axisymmetric body. His work included noise results from an acoustic microphone array and near-

field flow measurements from time-resolved particle image velocimetry (TR-PIV), wake pressure probes, and hot-wire anemometry. Coupled with phased-array beamforming techniques, he was able to identify noise sources and directivity patterns across a range of operating conditions. It was concluded, among other findings, that the directivity of noise radiated due to the unsteady loading of the blade was primarily directed along the blade normals, which accounted for the apparent shifting of the noise sources with respect to observer position. A detailed flow field analysis of a rotor positioned over a flat surface was conducted by de Vries *et al.*²⁵ They made use of unsteady surface pressure and force balance measurements in addition to TR-PIV to better understand the flow behavior of the propeller-boundary layer interaction. Although no acoustic measurements were reported, they were able to visualize the generation and propagation of tip vortices in greater detail, finding that the vortices self-induce a vertical velocity component after being generated, causing them to impact the surface flow in the wake. This form of flow-field analysis can be useful when identifying potential noise sources for the BLI configuration. They also observed the tip clearance to have no significant effect on the propeller thrust. Recent advancements have been made to model the tonal noise and performance of a propeller through the use of machine learning, however, as yet they have not been comprehensively applied to the BLI configuration.²⁶

Despite the growing research effort to examine and understand the acoustic characteristics and generation mechanisms of a BLI propulsor, there remains a notable knowledge gap. Notably, the effect of boundary layer thickness and turbulence contents on the emitted noise spectra and the associated acoustic directivity have not been studied in detail. Therefore, the present study aims to quantify the far-field acoustics generated by a two-bladed propeller ingesting turbulent boundary layers with varying boundary layer thicknesses and turbulence characteristics, by performing a series of acoustic measurements using two polar microphone arrays. In addition, by using hot-wire anemometry to determine the velocity and turbulence profiles of the different boundary layers, both with and without the propeller, the inflow conditions can be related to the observed modifications of the emitted noise. In conjunction with the acoustic and velocity measurements, by using an angular encoder, the results are also phase-averaged such that additional information is obtained on the variations of noise and velocity perturbations over a blade rotation, which provides a more comprehensive description of how the turbulence interaction impacts the near-field hydrodynamics and far-field acoustics, thus improving the physical understanding of the acoustic characteristics of the BLI configuration.

This paper is structured as follows: Sec. II describes the experimental setup, including the data acquisition and post-processing techniques employed in the study. The boundary layer characteristics as well as the influence of the propeller on the flow and turbulence development within the turbulent boundary layer are reported in Sec. III, which is followed by the far-field acoustic results, including the directivity patterns, in Sec. IV. By extracting the phase information from synchronous measurements, phase-averaged acoustics and flow-field results are presented and discussed in Sec. V. Section VI provides the concluding remarks from the present work.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Wind tunnel facility

All measurements presented in this work were conducted in the aeroacoustic wind tunnel facility at the University of Bristol. The

FIG. 1. Schematic of the boundary layer ingestion experimental setup with (a) isometric view, (b) side view, and (c) front view with definition of parameters.

facility is a temperature-controlled, closed-circuit, open-jet anechoic wind tunnel. The flow is exhausted from a nozzle with exit dimensions of 775 mm in height and 500 mm in width and can achieve freestream velocities of up to 40 m/s. The flow is highly uniform across its exit plane, with less than 0.2% turbulence intensity across the jet core. The settling chamber, contraction nozzle, test section and collector are located inside an anechoic chamber which measures 7.9 m in length, 5.0 m in width, and 4.6 m in height. The anechoic chamber enables acoustic measurements down to 160 Hz. For further specifics regarding the design and performance of wind tunnel and anechoic test chamber, the reader is advised to refer to Mayer *et al.*^{27,28}

B. Boundary layer ingestion test rig

The general assembly of the boundary layer ingestion (BLI) test rig is provided in Fig. 1. The setup consists of a two-bladed propeller mounted on an aluminum rig, which is positioned such that the propeller is adjacent to a flat plate. The flat plate used in these tests are made of three laser-cut pieces of 5 mm thick acrylic and is 2 m in width and 1.69 m in streamwise length. The propeller is placed 1 m downstream of the nozzle exit. The dimensions of the plate have been designed with considerations of boundary layer development length, potential for undesirable flow interaction with the plate edges, and edge acoustic scattering effects. To further reduce noise contamination due to flow and acoustic interaction with the plate edges, the flat plate is bordered with porous material. The details of the propeller rig itself are described in Sec. II C.

A two-bladed propeller, based on a Clark-Y profile, with a diameter of $D = 12''$ ($R = 152.4$ mm), and a pitch-to-diameter ratio of 1.5, was used in this study. Figure 2 shows the pitch angle and chord length distribution of the blade. The gap between the blade tip and the plate was fixed at $c = 5$ mm ($c/R = 0.033$), and the freestream velocity was maintained at $U_\infty = 30$ m/s throughout the study. A representative

FIG. 2. Distribution of the pitch angle and chord length of the 12'' × 18'' propeller blade.

condition of advance ratio, $J = 0.91$ (i.e., 6500 RPM), is reported in this work. Conceptual BLI aircraft operate at advance ratios similar to this value, such as the ONERA NOVA, and NASA D8, which have been studied at $J = 0.907$ and $J = 1.07 - 1.14$, respectively.^{29,30} At this moderate advance ratio, a high degree of acoustic haystacking is not expected.^{23,31}

Three tripping devices were used to achieve distinct thicknesses of the boundary layer at the propeller location thereby facilitating the investigation of BLI noise across a range of turbulent boundary layers. Here, the boundary layer thickness, δ , was evaluated based on 99% of the freestream velocity. The tripping devices were placed just downstream of the nozzle exit, i.e., 1 m upstream of the propeller disk, as seen in Fig. 1(a). The details of each trip, including the measured porosity of the metal foam, are listed in Table I. The selection of the tripping devices was performed with the goal of producing three boundary layers with distinct thicknesses and turbulence contents to represent a range of possible BLI scenarios and implementations, and to isolate behaviors that are influenced by the boundary layer properties. The materials chosen were selected to ensure the resulting boundary layer at the rotor plane exhibited canonical properties, as will be discussed in Sec. III A. In particular, the highly permeable porous metal foam blocks (Trips B and C) used in this study were chosen carefully to produce thick boundary layers with minimum pressure gradient effects at the downstream locations, as reported in earlier studies.^{32–34}

Prior to the BLI experiments, the boundary layers developed from the three trips, in the absence of the propeller, were characterized and evaluated by hot-wire anemometry. The characterization of the boundary layers produced from these three tripping devices is detailed in Sec. III.

C. Propeller rig

The general schematic of the propeller rig setup is provided in Fig. 3. The streamlined propeller rig houses a 2.7 kW Scorpion SII-4035-250 kV BLDC (brushless direct current) motor system, coupled to an RLS RE36 13-bit absolute angular encoder. The encoder enables synchronous acquisition of the propeller blade position in conjunction with the acoustic and flow-field measurements. The aluminum nacelle housing encloses the aforementioned components to reduce motor noise contamination and flow interference with the internal components. The internal structure and component arrangement can be seen in Fig. 3. The internal temperature of the rig is continuously monitored using several K-type thermocouples attached to the motor mount. Cooling is achieved via regulated compressed air injection from the aeroacoustic facility’s main supply, with the exhaust air vented from the rear of the propeller rig. The propeller is closed-loop RPM controlled with RPM feedback via a Monarch ROLS-P-25 laser

FIG. 3. Diagram depicting the internal structure of the propeller rig.

tachometer. It is useful to mention that a preliminary study confirmed that the thrust produced from the BLI configuration showed very limited change to that of the isolated case and, hence, is not presented in the current paper.

D. Far-field noise measurements

The far-field noise was captured by two polar microphone arrays, fitted with GRAS 40PL free-field microphones, with a frequency response range of 10 Hz–20 kHz and a dynamic range of 142 dB. As shown in Fig. 1, the two microphone arrays are arranged parallel and orthogonal to the plate, and have microphones spaced 5° apart. The parallel arc has 21 microphones with polar angles ranging from $\theta = 35^\circ$ to $\theta = 135^\circ$. The orthogonal array has 25 microphones that span $\phi = 25^\circ$ to $\phi = 145^\circ$, both arrays are placed 1.75 m from the propeller hub. Note that smaller polar angles indicate a location closer to the nozzle exit plane (i.e., upstream).

Measurements from all microphones are recorded synchronously using a National Instruments acquisition system with NI PXIe-4499 acquisition cards mounted in a PXIe-1082 chassis. The data were sampled at a frequency of 2^{16} Hz for an acquisition duration of 32 s at each condition. The power spectral density (PSD) of the acoustic data was computed via Welch’s method,³⁶ using a Hamming window with 50% overlap and a window size of 2^{14} samples, resulting in a frequency resolution of 4 Hz. The sound pressure level (SPL) was calculated from the PSD by

$$SPL = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{PSD(f)\Delta f}{P_{ref}^2} \right), \quad (1)$$

where $p_{ref} = 2 \times 10^{-5}$ Pa and $\Delta f = 4$ Hz. The background noise of the plain turbulent boundary layers was not seen to increase between the trips. Additionally, the measured BLI noise, including the blade passing frequency (BPF) tone and its harmonics, present results well above the background noise. However, it should be remarked that for Trips A and B, the broadband components are similar to that of the background noise at $f < 800$ Hz and $f < 350$ Hz, respectively, and should be interpreted with caution.

TABLE I. Table of tripping device properties.^{33,35}

Trip name	Material	Width (mm)	Height (mm)	Porosity, ϕ (%)
Trip A	80-grit Sandpaper	25	2	...
Trip B	45 PPI Iron Foam	50	5	85
Trip C	25 PPI Iron Foam	25	10	90

E. Hot-wire anemometry measurements

The boundary layer velocity measurements, both with and without the presence of the propeller, were carried out using the Dantec 55P16 single-wire probe, with a platinum-plated tungsten wire of $5\ \mu\text{m}$ in diameter and $1.25\ \text{mm}$ in length. A total of four streamwise measurement locations, upstream of the propeller and normal to the plate at $x = -0.06R, -0.12R, -0.2R, -0.3R$ were taken, where the negative sign indicates upstream of the propeller. The closest point measured was $y = 1.5\ \text{mm}$ from the surface. Note that $x = 0$ coincides with the propeller location, see Fig. 1. To resolve the profile close to the plate surface, measurement points along each line were distributed with increasing density nearer the plate. The hot-wire probe was mounted on a Thorlabs LTS300M 2D traverse system to allow automated, accurate positioning of the probe down to $\pm 5\ \mu\text{m}$. The probes were calibrated prior to each measurement session using a Dantec 54H10 calibrator. The hot-wire measurements were acquired at a sampling frequency of $2^{15}\ \text{Hz}$ for $16\ \text{s}$ at each location, with an uncertainty within $\pm 1\%$.

To allow examination of the possible changes induced by the propeller on the incoming turbulent structures, the blade passing frequency, $\text{BPF} = nB$, where n is revolutions per second and B is the number of blades, and its harmonics were first filtered from the velocity time-series. This was necessary because the periodic “pulses” of the velocity signals due to the rotation of the blade prevent an accurate evaluation of the broadband components of the velocity field, which are directly related to the turbulent structures within the boundary layer.³⁷ In this study, a finite impulse response (FIR) comb filter was used to achieve this tonal filtering. The FIR filter allows for individual specification of each of the band-stop notches. Thus, for each measurement point, the tonal peaks associated with the BPF and the harmonics were identified, and the notch parameters were constructed around them such that the entire spectral peak was attenuated to close to broadband levels. The passband ripple, i.e., the allowable deviation that occurs outside of the prescribed notch-bands, was set to 5% ; however, no adverse effects were seen outside of the notch-bands.

F. Phase-averaging methodology

Each measurement sample of the acoustic and velocity time-series has a corresponding blade angle position (α), see Fig. 1(c), as recorded by the synchronized RE36 angular encoder. This allows the application of phase-averaging, as depicted in Fig. 4, to obtain information on the variation of the measured quantities over the course of a blade rotation. Phase-averaging the acoustic signal, for example, can yield information on the precise blade phase angle that results in the largest far-field noise generation. The peak noise generation amplitude, location, and distribution over the blade angles can be useful, in conjunction with the knowledge of the degree of ingestion at each blade angle, to draw inferences on the sources of BLI noise, and its sensitivities to varying the incoming turbulent boundary layer. Additionally, applying this technique to the upstream flow velocity measurements can highlight the influence of the blade passage on the incoming boundary layer profiles and can be related to the phased acoustic results.

To enable analysis of the acoustic signals, they were first filtered using a bandpass filter to isolate the useful frequency range ($160\ \text{Hz}$ to $20\ \text{kHz}$). Then, for each integer blade angle value α , a bin of width $\Delta\alpha = \pm 0.5^\circ$ is constructed. Since for a two-bladed propeller, the phase repeats every 180° , the bins span from $\alpha = -90^\circ$ to 90° , with $\alpha = 0^\circ$ representing the perpendicular position, i.e., when the blade tip is closest to the plate. The measurement samples are then sorted into their respective bins, as shown graphically in Fig. 4, where the sorting of samples for an arbitrary bin is depicted, with both the encoder and measured quantity time series as reference.

It should be noted that in the case of the acoustic signals, the encoder values were offset by the phase lag introduced by the time it takes for the sound to propagate to the microphone. The propagation distance in this case was taken to be the distance from the microphone to the rotor hub. To clarify, the current method does not distinguish between the noise generated by each blade and instead reports the noise emitted by the entire rotor disk. This method is useful in

FIG. 4. Diagram showing the phase-averaging technique applied here to an example signal for a single bin of width $2\Delta\alpha$. Samples are selectively binned according to their respective blade angle value, α . Note that this diagram depicts a larger bin width for visual clarity.

TABLE II. A summary of the boundary layer properties of the three tripping devices, as measured at the propeller plane ($x = 0$ m) without the propeller at $U_\infty = 30$ m/s.

Trip name	Boundary layer thickness (δ) (mm)	Displacement thickness (δ^*) (mm)	Momentum thickness (θ^*) (mm)	Normalized thickness (δ/R)
Trip A	20.5	2.7	2.1	0.13
Trip B	42.5	4.5	3.6	0.28
Trip C	101.0	12.2	9.8	0.66

situations where the blades are expected to produce different noise characteristics at different points in the rotation, i.e., non-axisymmetric inflows, to observe the variation of noise generation with blade phase. Each α bin was then processed individually, to calculate the root mean square (RMS) of the pressure fluctuations (p_{rms}) per bin. This method removes the influence of the BPF tone as the mean is subtracted for each bin, and thus, the acoustic results presented in Sec. V reflect the level of broadband noise present at each blade angle. The selected bin resolution translates to an uncertainty in the phasing of $\pm 0.5^\circ$. The phase-dependent far-field SPL can then be found from

$$SPL_\alpha = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{p_{rms}(\alpha)}{p_{ref}} \right), \quad (2)$$

where $p_{ref} = 2 \times 10^{-5}$ Pa. Regarding the velocity data, collected using the hot-wire technique described in Sec. II E, a similar post-processing method is used. Subsequently, each α bin containing the phased velocity samples is processed to produce mean and RMS velocity data, resulting in an individual mean and RMS velocity value for each bin at each measurement location. The results of this phase-averaging technique on the acoustic and velocity measurements are presented in Sec. V.

III. BOUNDARY LAYER CHARACTERISTICS

A. Development of the turbulent boundary layers without propeller

Prior to discussing the acoustic results of the installed BLI configuration, it is necessary to first characterize and compare the boundary layer profiles produced by the three different trips, and their turbulence energy contents. Boundary layer canonicity must also be established to ensure suitability for the current study. The measurements were taken at the propeller position, $x = 0$ (1 m from the nozzle exit), when the propeller is absent and with $U_\infty = 30$ m/s. The hot-wire probe was traversed a distance of 200 mm from the plate to capture the entire boundary layer region. Each of the three trips were affixed to the plate at the nozzle exit, as depicted in Fig. 1. As expected, the use of these three tripping devices leads to boundary layers with significantly different boundary layer thicknesses. Table II summarizes the boundary layer thickness (δ), which is based on 99% of the freestream velocity, displacement thickness (δ^*), and momentum thickness (θ^*), for the three trips, at $U_\infty = 30$ m/s.

The mean and root mean square (RMS) velocity profiles for the boundary layers produced using the three different tripping devices are shown in Fig. 5. In Fig. 5(a), the mean velocity profiles for the three boundary layers exhibit a high degree of similarity and conform to the conventional turbulent boundary layer profiles observed in previous works.^{32,38} In contrast, the RMS velocity profiles shown in Fig. 5(b) highlight clear distinctions among the three trips, with the resulting

boundary layer energy content clearly increasing with trip severity. As can be seen, Trip C, the thickest trip, produces the largest velocity fluctuations from close to the wall to the outer region of the boundary layer with the largest deviation from Trips A and B occurring at $y/\delta = 0.5$. The notably distinct RMS profile for Trip C indicates significant changes in the energy contents of the boundary layer; however, it has been verified through static pressure measurements that there are no significant pressure gradient effects.

FIG. 5. Boundary layer characteristics for the three trips measured at the propeller plane ($x = 0$), normalized by the respective boundary layer thicknesses (δ), as listed in Table II. (a) Mean velocity profiles and (b) RMS of the velocity profiles at $U_\infty = 30$ m/s.

The boundary layer profiles, expressed in wall units of $u^+ - y^+$, at the propeller location, $x = 0$ m, are shown in Fig. 6. Here, u^+ and y^+ are evaluated as

$$u^+ = \frac{u_{\text{mean}}}{u_\tau}, \tag{3}$$

$$y^+ = \frac{y u_\tau}{\nu}, \tag{4}$$

where u_{mean} is the time-averaged flow velocity, $u_\tau = \sqrt{\tau_w/\rho}$ is the friction velocity in which $\tau_w = \frac{1}{2}\rho C_f U_\infty^2$ is the wall shear stress, ρ is the density of air, C_f is the skin friction coefficient calculated using a modified Prandtl formulation, $C_f = 0.074 Re_x^{-0.2}$. Here, Re_x is the Reynolds number in the streamwise direction,³⁹ and ν is the kinematic viscosity.

To verify that the resulting boundary layer, developed after each trip, remains primarily canonical at the propeller location, theoretical predictions from both Spalding and Coles^{40–42} were determined based on Eqs. (5) and (6), respectively, for comparison as

$$y^+ = u^+ + 0.1108 \left[e^{0.4u^+} - 1 - 0.4u^+ - \frac{(0.4u^+)^2}{2!} - \frac{(0.4u^+)^3}{3!} - \frac{(0.4u^+)^4}{4!} \right], \tag{5}$$

$$u^+ = \frac{1}{k} \ln y^+ + C + 2 \frac{\Pi}{k} \sin^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{2} \cdot \frac{y^+}{\delta} \right), \tag{6}$$

where $k = 0.4$ is the von Kármán constant, $C = 4.9$, and $\Pi = 0.51$. These analytical predictions are superimposed onto the experimental results in Fig. 6. It can be observed that the boundary layers developed from Trips A and B closely follow Spalding’s solution in the log-law region, while that from Trip C deviates slightly. Additionally, the Trip C boundary layer shows a comparable trend to Coles’ prediction, which has been widely used as an estimator in the log-layer and outer regions of turbulent boundary layers.⁴¹ The relatively strong agreement with both Spalding and Coles’ solutions shows that the turbulent boundary layers developed from all three tripping devices do not significantly deviate from a canonical boundary layer at the propeller location.

FIG. 6. The turbulent boundary layers developed from Trips A, B, and C measured at the propeller plane ($x = 0$) in $u^+ - y^+$.

Additionally, comparisons of the power spectral density of the measured boundary layer velocity to the von Kármán spectrum can indicate the degree of isotropy of the turbulent flow.^{43–45} The von Kármán spectrum is defined as

$$\Phi_{uu}(f) = \frac{4u_{\text{rms}}^2 L}{U_\infty} \frac{1}{[1 + (k_x/k_e)^2]^{5/6}}, \tag{7}$$

where

$$\frac{k_x}{k_e} = 2\sqrt{\pi} \frac{\Gamma(1/3)}{\Gamma(5/6)} \frac{fL}{U_\infty}, \tag{8}$$

k_x is the streamwise wavenumber, k_e is the wavenumber range of the eddies, and Γ is the Gamma function. The integral length scales, L , were obtained through the autocorrelation analysis of the velocity data.⁴⁶ More details on this technique will be provided in Sec. III B 2. The velocity spectra (ϕ_{uu}), obtained at $y = 5$ mm away from the plate for the three tripping devices, and the comparison against the corresponding von Kármán spectra are provided in Fig. 7. As can be seen, an overall good agreement between the measured and predicted velocity spectra is achieved, further confirming the canonicity of the three turbulent boundary layers and their suitability for this study.

B. Development of the turbulent boundary layers with propeller ingestion

1. Effect of the propeller on the inflow velocity field

It is expected that the propeller will induce changes to the mean and fluctuating velocity profiles and potentially the turbulence length scales of the incoming turbulent boundary layers. Changes in the turbulence energy content and length scales have the potential to subsequently influence the far-field noise characteristics of the BLI configuration.⁴⁷ Therefore, it is valuable to first assess the aerodynamic effect of the propeller on the incoming turbulent boundary layers.

FIG. 7. Power spectral density of the three boundary layers measured at the tip location of $y = 5$ mm (markers) and comparison against the von Kármán spectra predictions (dashed lines).

The mean and RMS profiles of the velocity field are measured at $x = -0.06R, -0.12R, -0.2R, -0.3R$ upstream of the propeller and presented in Figs. 8 and 9 for the three boundary layers reported in Sec. III A. Note that the results are presented in terms of y/R , where R is the propeller radius. For ease of comparison, the velocity profiles in the presence of the propeller are marked with solid lines and those without the propeller are marked with dashed lines, for all three tripping devices. The boundary layer thicknesses ($y = \delta$), as measured without the propeller (see Table II), are marked at $y/R = 0.135, 0.280, \text{ and } 0.664$ for Trips A, B, and C, respectively, by a dashed line in Figs. 8 and 9. The “Tip Line” and “Hub Line” in the figures refer to the location of the blade tip and the propeller hub, respectively. Additionally, to better understand the changes occurring between the plate and blade tip, zoomed-in views of the tip gap region are presented below each plot.

From the mean velocity profiles shown in Fig. 8, the propeller noticeably accelerates the flow within the reference boundary layer

thicknesses at all upstream locations for all three trips. This is especially evident at the closest upstream location of $x = -0.06R$, where the separation between the “with propeller” and “without propeller” profiles is greatest. The increase in velocity observed due to the presence of the propeller slightly increases as the flow approaches the propeller, with maximum velocity observed at the $y = \delta$ boundary layer thickness line for Trips A and B.

More importantly, below the $y = \delta$ lines, the accelerated flow maintains a similar profile shape to that without the propeller, although accelerated. In contrast, outside the reference boundary layer region ($y > \delta$), dissimilar velocity profiles can be observed between the cases with and without the propeller. This suggests that within the boundary layer, the mean flow behavior is dominated by the boundary layer characteristics, but moving away from the boundary layer, the bulk velocity in the “freestream” flow region is more heavily influenced by the momentum changes imparted by the rotating propeller. Finally, it should be noted that, similar to within the boundary layer, the bulk

FIG. 8. Mean velocity profiles upstream of the propeller, with zoomed-in tip gap region for (a) Trip A, (b) Trip B, and (c) Trip C. The $y = \delta$ line denotes the boundary layer thicknesses as measured without the propeller, see Table II.

FIG. 9. Velocity RMS profiles upstream of the propeller for (a) Trip A, (b) Trip B, and (c) Trip C with comparison to the plain boundary layer and the filtered profiles as described in Sec. II E. Zoomed-in regions near the surface are also shown. The $y = \delta$ line denotes the boundary layer thicknesses as measured without the propeller, see Table II.

flow velocity also increases as it is convected toward the propeller. The propeller and no-propeller velocity profiles for all three boundary layers are observed to converge near $y/R = 0.66$. This crossing of the velocity profiles occurs due to the reduced propeller acceleration and velocity reduction effect as a result of the proximity to the propeller hub. The hub presents a blockage in the flow, seen clearly in Fig. 8(c) at the axial location of $x = -0.3R$ for positions $y/R > 0.66$. However, due to space constraints in front of the propeller at $-0.3R < x < 0.0R$, no measurement points are available beyond $y/R > 0.66$ at these streamwise locations. For Trip C, Fig. 8(c), the convergence also coincides with the $y = \delta$ location.

In general, the effect of the propeller on the boundary layer profiles across all boundary layer thicknesses is a consistent increase in mean velocity, increasing with proximity to the propeller, including within the tip gap region.

Figure 9 shows the corresponding velocity RMS profiles upstream of the propeller for each of the three different boundary layers at the four upstream locations. The velocity fluctuations consist primarily of two components: the strong periodic components due to the presence of the rotating blades, and the stochastic fluctuations due to the turbulence structures within the turbulent boundary layer. Therefore, to isolate the broadband components, the time-series signal of the velocity fluctuations is filtered, via the FIR filter technique described in Sec. II E, to remove the periodic components. Both the unfiltered (thick solid line) and filtered (thin solid line) results are presented in Fig. 9 together with the result from the case without the propeller (dashed line).

The effect of the propeller on the incoming boundary layer profiles without filtering will first be discussed, following which, the filtered profiles will then be compared. Focusing first on the comparison

between the unfiltered and no-propeller cases, it is clear that the periodic blade passage significantly increases the velocity fluctuations upstream of the propeller from $x = -0.06R$ to $x = -0.2R$. At the furthest upstream location of $x = -0.3R$, the fluctuations only exhibit a minor increase outside of the reference boundary layer thickness, above the $y = \delta$ line, for Trips A and B. This is in agreement with the changes in the mean velocity profile, where the $x = -0.3R$ location showed the smallest time-averaged acceleration due to the propeller. Moreover, a closer examination of the two cases (unfiltered and no-propeller) shows that the velocity fluctuations strongly increase upon approaching the propeller, within the respective boundary layers, due to proximity to the blade passage. It is useful to recall that the boundary layer thicknesses, as measured without the propeller are $y/R = 0.135, 0.280,$ and 0.664 for Trips A, B, and C, respectively, and are denoted in the plots by the $y = \delta$ line.

Previous studies by Murray *et al.*²³ and Hickling²⁴ showed that the far-field acoustics of a BLI configuration experienced prominent accentuation of the acoustic broadband component, due to increased turbulence ingestion noise. Hence, the RMS velocity results between the tone-filtered profiles and the no-propeller case will be compared, to assess the changes induced by the propeller on the turbulence content of the boundary layers, by filtering the pulsation of the propeller passage. In Fig. 9, the filtered RMS velocity profiles show distinct behavior compared to those of the unfiltered, with the filtered profiles almost coinciding with the results of the case without the propeller, regardless of the streamwise location. This is consistent across all three boundary layers, indicating the propeller minimally affects the incoming turbulence both within, and outside of, the reference boundary layer thickness. Upon comparison of the RMS velocity profiles of both the unfiltered and filtered cases, to the case without the propeller, it can be inferred that first the periodic blade passage intensifies the velocity fluctuations of the incoming flow; however, such increases are not significant within the turbulent boundary layers for all three tripping devices; second, modifications to the turbulence contents within the boundary layer by the propeller are minimal.

Examining the tip gap region, i.e., the space between the plate and the tip line, as shown by the zoomed-in plots in Fig. 9, the velocity fluctuations for the unfiltered case only slightly exceed that of the no-propeller case at $x = -0.06R$, across all trips, and reduces to comparable levels at further upstream positions. This indicates that the effect of propeller pulsation is not strongly present in the tip gap region. For the filtered case, a disparity is most evident for Trips A and B, where the filtered velocity fluctuations, and hence, the turbulence levels are slightly reduced when the propeller is present. It is proposed that this minor reduction comes from a streamline contraction effect close to the wall, as part of the inflow is convected through the tip gap, further evidenced by the increase in the disparity when approaching the propeller. Air flowing through a contraction, such as the current tip gap, can potentially stretch turbulent eddies and reduce local turbulence intensity. Due to the three-dimensional nature of the scenario and the inherent complexity of the flow field, this requires a more in-depth analysis using additional flow visualization techniques or high-fidelity simulations, to definitively identify the cause. From the velocity fluctuation results, it is noted that for the BLI configuration, acceleration of the mean velocity profiles is not necessarily accompanied by changes in velocity fluctuations. Since the latter is likely to have more impact on the far-field acoustics, caution should be exercised when relating

the mean aerodynamic performance to the noise emission of a BLI configuration.

2. Effects of the propeller on turbulence length scales

The presence of a thrusting propeller has the potential to induce stretching and distortion of the incoming turbulent structures. Evaluation of these changes to the flow structure can be analyzed through the calculation of the turbulence length scales. Hence, the turbulence length scales of each boundary layer, both with and without the propeller, are computed. The velocity signals were first filtered using the FIR technique described in Sec. II E, to remove the pulsation of the blade passing frequency and its harmonics, in order to accurately obtain the autocorrelation results of the turbulence components. Subsequently, the turbulence integral length scale, L , can be found using

$$L = U_\infty \int_0^{\tau_0} R_{u_i u_i}(\tau) d\tau, \tag{9}$$

where $R_{u_i u_i}(\tau)$ is the autocorrelation function, defined as

$$R_{u_i u_i}(\tau) = \frac{\overline{u_i'(t + \tau)u_i'(t)}}{u_{i,rms}^2}, \tag{10}$$

where u_i' is the velocity fluctuations at position i , τ denotes the time lag between the correlated velocity signals, and τ_0 is such that $R_{u_i u_i}(\tau_0)$ crosses zero. The turbulence length scales were calculated at the upstream location of $x = -0.06R$, for Trips A, B, and C, and compared with the no-propeller (plain boundary layer) case. Recall that $x = -0.06R$ represents the location closest to the propeller. Since only the turbulent structures within the boundary layer are of interest, the length scale profiles are presented within the $0 \leq y/\delta \leq 1$ range for each boundary layer case in Fig. 10. Additionally, the value of δ changes between trips, and hence, the blade tip location in Fig. 10 also changes and is denoted by the vertical dotted lines. Note that the

FIG. 10. Turbulence length scales at the upstream location of $x = -0.06R$ for all three trips. Both the no-propeller (line) and propeller (marker) cases are presented.

length scale, L , is normalized by the mean aerodynamic chord of the blade, $c_m = 18$ mm.

Intuitively, the turbulence length scales are observed to increase with boundary layer thickness, with Trip C presenting length scales 1.5 times larger than those from Trip B and 2.3 times larger than those of Trip A. It is worthwhile to note that the turbulence length scales within the entire Trip C boundary layer are greater than the blade mean aerodynamic chord ($L/c_m > 1$), which, as will be shown in the acoustic results in Sec. IV, could have strong implications regarding the broadband noise signature of the BLI configuration. Aside from the differences in magnitude between trips, the turbulence length scale profiles of Trips A and B, see Fig. 10, present comparable behavior, with length scales reducing consistently with increasing wall distance (y). All three boundary layers show a slight dip near the wall, but it is more pronounced in the case of Trips B and C. In the case of Trip C, the length scale profile exhibits a noticeable change in behavior when compared to the other two trips. The profile presents a broad increase in length scale that peaks near $y/\delta = 0.5$ in the form of a hump, this is in contrast to the steady decrease with y/δ observed previously in Trips A and B. It is interesting to note that the location of the hump for Trip C, $y/\delta = 0.5$, correlates closely with the peak RMS velocity observed for the Trip C boundary layer in Fig. 5. Within the tip gap (left of the vertical dashed line), it can be seen that the length scales reduce upon approaching the wall, however, this behavior is also seen in the no-propeller case, thus the reduction is unlikely to be due to the propeller influence. The length scale changes induced by the propeller for Trips A and B are observed to be minimal, as shown by the indiscernible differences between the markers and line for Trips A and B in Fig. 10. For Trip C, the propeller is seen to have a slightly stronger effect on the profile, presenting a general reduction in length scales with the propeller present, outside of the tip gap region.

It should be remarked that at the studied operating condition of $J = 0.91$, a severe stretching of the turbulence structures by the propeller is not expected. Hickling²⁴ proposed a criterion that predicts the occurrence of haystacking by relating the rotational speed of the propeller to the incoming flow speed and thus eddy convection through the rotor plane. The criterion is defined as $B\Omega L/U_\infty \gg 1$, where B is blade number, Ω is the propeller angular velocity, and L is axial turbulent length scale. Taking Trip C as an example here with the greatest eddy size, where $L \simeq 0.025$ m, the criterion is determined to be $B\Omega L/U_\infty \simeq 1.03$, which is only marginally above 1. Hence, a high degree of inflow eddy stretching, blade-to-blade correlation, and therefore, haystacking in the acoustic spectra is not expected. This will be demonstrated in Sec. IV.

IV. FAR-FIELD ACOUSTICS

In this section, the results of the far-field acoustic measurements are presented and discussed. First, the acoustic spectra of selected locations from each array are presented for all three boundary layers, see Table II. As the tip-plate gap is kept constant throughout, the increasing boundary layer thicknesses directly correspond to an increase in boundary layer ingestion. The sound pressure level (SPL) spectra allow a direct assessment of the effect of the boundary layer thickness and turbulence contents on the far-field noise of BLI, in terms of both tonal and broadband components. Second, the directivity patterns of the far-field noise are presented for the same boundary layer conditions to highlight the modification in noise propagation directivity as boundary layer properties are varied.

A. Acoustic spectra analyses

This subsection will discuss the far-field acoustic spectra of the BLI cases. Figures 11 and 12 show the far-field SPL spectra at three polar angles of $\theta = 55^\circ, 90^\circ$, and 125° from the parallel arc, and $\phi = 55^\circ, 90^\circ$, and 110° from the orthogonal arc, respectively, see Fig. 1(a). Recall that the polar angles are defined such that the smaller angles are located upstream with respect to the freestream direction. The parallel arc spectra are presented in Fig. 11, where the most distinct change in the acoustic spectra is the notable increase in the broadband noise contents with increasing boundary layer ingestion, common to all three observer angles. This is intuitive as the propeller is ingesting significantly more turbulence from the incoming boundary layer, as determined in Sec. III B 2, and is consistent with previous studies.^{23,24} With increasing boundary layer thickness, the mid to high frequencies exhibit a consistent and significant increase in broadband levels, which is more pronounced at downstream polar angles ($\theta = 125^\circ$), as shown by the greater separation of spectra in Fig. 11(c) as compared to angles $\theta = 55^\circ$ and 90° in Figs. 11(a) and 11(b), further upstream. The overall directivity pattern will be covered in more detail in Sec. IV B. Recall that Trip C has greater velocity energy content and length scales larger than the mean aerodynamic chord, as discussed in Sec. III, distinct from both Trips A and B. Therefore, the extent of boundary layer ingestion and its turbulence characteristics have an observable effect on the broadband frequency range and the magnitude of its accentuation. Focusing only on the polar angle of $\theta = 125^\circ$ in Fig. 11(c), the frequency at which the broadband noise increase initiates consistently shifts to lower frequencies as boundary layer ingestion increases. For example, the broadband increase begins almost immediately after the blade pass frequency of 240 Hz for Trip C, whereas for Trips B and C, this begins at approximately $f = 500$ and 2600 Hz, respectively. This is due to the presence of larger turbulent structures within the Trip C boundary layer, as seen in Sec. III B, causing the broadband noise elevation to extend to lower frequencies. Notably absent is the presence of spectral haystacking in the broadband spectra, indicating a lack of significant blade-to-blade correlation. Taking the turbulence length scale results in Sec. III B 2 and the plain boundary layer results as shown in Fig. 5, together with the acoustic spectra, it can be said that the large broadband increases seen in the parallel array with the thicker boundary layers are likely attributed to the greater turbulence contents and larger turbulence length scales within the boundary layer being ingested by the propeller, rather than the presence of the propeller and its modification of the turbulent structures (inflow distortion). In addition, there is also a distinct lack of blade trailing edge self-noise in the presented spectra. Trailing edge noise is conventionally a prominent factor in propeller noise emissions,⁴⁸ however, in the presence of non-axisymmetrical inflows or strong turbulence ingestion, the turbulence ingestion noise sources typically exceed and obscure the contributions of trailing edge noise, except in the case of high thrust conditions.⁴⁹ The current operating condition of $J = 0.91$ presents a mild thrust case and it is thus observed to present strong BLI noise contributions and an absence of a clear trailing edge noise signature.

To examine the effect of BLI on the tonal components of the spectra, a close-up view of the tonal peaks associated with the blade pass frequency, BPF ($f/\text{BPF} = 1$), and its first harmonic, 2xBPF ($f/\text{BPF} = 2$), are also included in Fig. 11, for each of the presented polar angles. Subsequent BPF harmonics are obscured by the large

FIG. 11. Far-field acoustic spectra from the parallel array for (a) $\theta = 55^\circ$, (b) $\theta = 90^\circ$, and (c) $\theta = 125^\circ$, with zoomed-in regions for the 1xBPF and 2xBPF tonal peaks.

broadband increases for the thicker boundary layers and are therefore not examined. At all presented polar angles in the parallel array, the tonal peak at the BPF increases only slightly with increasing boundary layer thickness, while the peaks at the first harmonic are more strongly affected. Similar to the broadband component, changes in the 2xBPF peak are directly related to the degree of boundary layer ingestion, i.e., thicker boundary layers give rise to greater 2xBPF tonal increases. It is expected that the BPF is minimally affected by BLI as changes in unsteady loading are reflected predominantly in the higher harmonics.⁴¹ Furthermore, the tonal increase grows along the downstream direction, illustrated by the increasing gap between the BLI cases across all three tripping devices. The changes in BPF tones further confirm that the acoustic effect of the BLI configuration is more prominent at downstream observer angles in the parallel direction. A thorough examination of the BPF directivity will be presented in Sec. IV B.

Figure 12 shows the acoustic spectra for the orthogonal array under the same conditions at observer polar angles of $\phi = 55^\circ, 90^\circ$, and 110° . In this orthogonal direction, the observed acoustic spectra exhibit different behavior from those previously observed in the parallel array. Unlike in the parallel direction, where the broadband component of all three boundary layers significantly increases, directed strongly downstream, the broadband noise in the orthogonal direction shows marginal differences between Trips A and B, with no evident trend

with varying observer angles as shown in Fig. 12. Only minor increases at mid frequencies can be seen at $\phi = 55^\circ$ and 110° for Trip B. For Trip C, however, the far-field spectra do show some marked differences. First, an increase in broadband noise is observed and occurs across all presented observer angles. Second, the broadband increase occurs over the entire mid-to-high frequency range from approximately $f = 300\text{--}10\,000$ Hz. Moreover, contrary to the parallel direction, the broadband increase for Trip C appears to be more pronounced at the upstream polar angle of $\phi = 55^\circ$, rather than angles downstream. Yet, the increase exhibits random magnitude variations over the frequency range (i.e., inconsistent hump) as compared to that in the parallel direction, indicating potentially different noise generation mechanisms or propagation characteristics. In general, the increase in broadband noise components in the orthogonal direction is not as pronounced as in the parallel direction and is slightly biased upstream.

The changes in the tonal characteristics by the BLI configuration in the orthogonal direction also differ from those in the parallel array. Again, Fig. 12 shows the zoomed-in views of the tonal peaks associated with the BPF and its first harmonic, 2xBPF, for each of the three polar angles. In the orthogonal direction, the tonal peak at the BPF does not show significant magnitude variations as boundary layer ingestion increases. As will be seen in Sec. IV B, the response of the first harmonic, 2xBPF, is complex and highly dependent on observer position.

FIG. 12. Far field acoustic spectra from the orthogonal array for (a) $\phi = 55^\circ$, (b) $\phi = 90^\circ$, and (c) $\phi = 110^\circ$, with zoomed-in sections for the 1xBPF and 2xBPF tonal peaks.

The subsequent BPF harmonics for Trip A are not visible, which is in direct contrast to the spectra in the parallel array where these harmonics are discernible until approximately 4000 Hz. Indicating that unsteady loading noise presents a reduced contribution to the noise signature in this orthogonal direction.

B. Directivity analyses

This subsection will discuss the far-field acoustic directivity patterns of the BLI cases. To obtain a comprehensive understanding of the noise propagation, the overall sound pressure level (OASPL) directivity patterns, as well as the directivity of the first and second tones (BPF and 2xBPF) are calculated in both the parallel and orthogonal arcs and plotted for all three BLI cases. The OASPL is evaluated for both arrays by

$$OASPL = 10 \log_{10} \int_{f_1}^{f_2} \frac{PSD(f)}{P_{ref}^2} df, \tag{11}$$

where $f_1 = 160$ Hz and $f_2 = 10\,000$ Hz.

The OASPL directivity for the parallel and orthogonal directions are presented in Figs. 13(a) and 13(b), respectively. The effect of BLI properties on far-field noise directivity differs between the parallel and orthogonal directions. In the parallel arc, the directivity pattern exhibits cardioid-like features, with clear noise increases in downstream

polar angles when increasing boundary layer ingestion (i.e., with thicker boundary layers), in agreement with the spectral results discussed in Sec. IV A. The greatest increase in noise levels was observed at the furthest downstream angle, $\theta = 135^\circ$, with an increase in 7.7 dB between Trip A and Trip C. Based on the observations from Fig. 11, the substantial OASPL noise increase at the downstream polar angles ($\theta > 90^\circ$) can be attributed to the increase in the mid to high frequency broadband energy content at these observer locations. Also, the maximum OASPL in this parallel direction is found to gradually shift further downstream as the boundary layer ingestion increases.

In contrast to the cardioid-like directivity patterns in the parallel direction, the OASPL directivity in the plate-orthogonal direction is distinctly more dipole-like. The pattern shows a consistent maximum at $\phi = 90^\circ$ across the three considered BLI cases, with the only variation occurring at the upstream polar angles ($30^\circ < \phi < 75^\circ$), as shown in Fig. 13(b). The strong downstream BLI effects seen in the parallel arc are not present in the orthogonal direction.

Figures 14(a) and 14(b) show the SPL directivity patterns of the BPF (216.67 Hz) in both the parallel and orthogonal microphone arcs, while Figs. 14(c) and 14(d) present that of the 2xBPF harmonic tone. Focusing initially on the BPF tone in Figs. 14(a) and 14(b), these directivity patterns bear similar profiles to that of their respective OASPL directivity shown in Fig. 13, however, with significantly reduced variations between the BLI cases, implying minimal changes to steady blade

FIG. 13. Overall sound pressure level directivity patterns with increasing boundary layer thickness for (a) parallel array and (b) orthogonal array. Note that flow is from right to left.

loading. Comparing Figs. 13(a) and 14(a), the level of variation in the BPF magnitude at downstream locations is minor in comparison with that observed in the OASPL results, further evidencing the significant contribution of broadband noise in BLI configurations. In the orthogonal array, shown in Fig. 14(b), the effect of the boundary layer thickness on the BPF tone is found to be minimal, consistent with the OASPL results presented in Fig. 13(b). Subsequently, the directivity for the first harmonic of the BPF (2xBPF) is presented in Figs. 14(c) and 14(d). The 2xBPF tone directivity in the parallel array is comparable with the OASPL directivity pattern [Fig. 13(b)], showing clear increases with boundary layer thickness at downstream angles. However, the directivity pattern for the orthogonal direction, as seen in Fig. 14(d), becomes relatively complex with no clear trend other than clear increases far upstream and far downstream with boundary layer thickness.

Taking a closer look at the OASPL and BPF directivity patterns from Figs. 13(a) and 14(c), it is clear that the directivity patterns of the parallel array present significant sensitivities to BLI contributions, strongly affecting downstream polar angles $\theta > 90^\circ$ with minor increases toward the most upstream angles and a minimum at approximately $\theta = 55^\circ$. Previously, Hickling²⁴ provided empirical evidence demonstrating that the acoustic directivity pattern for a propeller ingesting turbulent flow is predominantly propagated in a direction parallel to the blade normals. Consequently, in the current study, it is suggested that the observed directivity patterns are strongly influenced by the pitch angle of the blades. This is supported by the following

FIG. 14. Directivity patterns of the BPF (216.67 Hz) tone (a) and (b) and the 2xBPF (433.34 Hz) tone (c) and (d) for the parallel array and orthogonal arrays, for three different BLI configurations. Note that flow is from right to left.

observations, first, when the blade is immersed in the boundary layer, the normal vectors of the immersed blade sections are oriented toward the downstream portion of the parallel array, where the strongest broadband noise increases are measured. Second, the orthogonal array sees significantly reduced broadband noise increases with increasing boundary layer thickness, as the blade normals are not oriented toward this array at phase angles where the blade is immersed in the boundary layers. Thus, by careful consideration of the blade normal vector orientation during blade-boundary-layer interaction, it is possible to direct the broadband BLI noise emissions as desired, providing a useful avenue for BLI noise directivity optimization during aircraft design. However, following the same reasoning, there must also exist a normal vector of the blade oriented upstream and opposite the parallel array. While not measured in the current experimental setup, it is likely that this upstream direction would also experience an increase in BLI broadband noise. The upstream increases observed in the orthogonal array, shown in Fig. 13(b), may also be partially due to this phenomenon. Additionally, the current results may include boundary layer refraction effects, which are not studied here as the effect is assumed to be negligible for the current operating conditions.⁵⁰

V. PHASE-AVERAGED AEROACOUSTIC ANALYSIS

The results presented in Secs. III and IV discussed the time-averaged quantities relating to the inflow velocity field and far-field noise. To further investigate the detailed dynamics of propeller-boundary-layer interaction, the acoustic and velocity measurements were “phase-locked” with the synchronized phase information from the angular encoder to obtain phase-averaged results, illustrating the changes of both near-field velocity and far-field acoustics over a rotation of the propeller. The phase-averaged post-processing methodology is described in Sec. II F. The results will be discussed with reference to the four distinct propeller BLI stages, as depicted in Fig. 15, namely, the approach phase, where the blade has entered the boundary layer and is approaching the plate; the perpendicular phase, where the blade is at its closest point to the wall; the retreat phase, where the blade is retreating from the wall and exits the boundary layer; and finally the non-ingestion phase, where no part of the propeller is interacting with the boundary layer. The blade angle (α) range of each phase is dependent upon the boundary layer thickness (δ), and thus, the critical blade angle (α_δ) is used to denote the transition between the phases. The critical blade angle is defined as the blade angle at which the blade tip meets the edge of the boundary layer thickness as shown in Fig. 15.

Figure 16(a) presents the phase-averaged SPL results from the $\theta = 90^\circ$ microphone in the parallel array for Trips A, B, and C, see Table II, against blade angle (α). It should first be noted that the results are primarily associated with the broadband components, owing to the present approach of evaluating the RMS for each bin of the acoustic pressure signal, i.e., the tonal contributions are largely filtered out (refer to Sec. II F for details). The highlighted segments of each line denote the range of α angles where the blade is immersed in the respective boundary layers, i.e., $-\alpha_\delta < \alpha < \alpha_\delta$. Immediately clear for all three boundary layers is the presence of a hump profile across the rotation with a peak at the $\alpha = -5^\circ$ blade angle. The magnitude and width of the humps about this peak are observed to vary significantly between the different boundary layers. The hump for Trip A, the thinnest boundary layer, spans from $\alpha = -20^\circ$ to 10° . Expectedly, this range is increased in the cases of Trips B and C. The hump width is observed to closely correlate with the boundary layer thickness, and therefore, the range of the respective critical blade angles (α_δ) as defined in Fig. 15. In other words, the hump region of increased noise spans the range of blade angles where the blade interacts with the boundary layer, denoted by the highlighted segments in Fig. 16(a). It is also seen in Fig. 16(a) that the α angle of the hump peak does not vary significantly with boundary layer thickness, remaining in the approach phase close to $\alpha = -5^\circ$. During the non-ingestion phase of the rotation, differences are still observed between the boundary layers, with Trip B only slightly above Trip A, while Trip C presents a clear increase. The presence of these differences outside of the approach and retreating phases signifies the possibility of increased general turbulence ingestion due to the presence of heightened levels of turbulence, which increases the minimum level of generated turbulence ingestion noise. However, further investigation using high-fidelity simulations, or phase-averaged blade surface loading measurements, would need to be performed to fully define the flow mechanisms of this observation.

Figures 16(b)–16(d) expand the phased acoustic results across the full parallel array to assess the directional properties of the phase-averaged acoustics for each boundary layer. Figure 16(b) presents the directivity-phase contour for Trip A, where the bias of higher noise levels toward downstream angles seen in Sec. IV B is also clearly observed. Additionally, the peak location is seen not to vary significantly from the $\alpha = -5^\circ$ phase with directivity angle (θ), although there is a minor, yet noticeable shifting, where far downstream angles, such as $\theta = 130^\circ$, experience the peak at blade angles slightly earlier in the rotation, visible by the diagonal characteristics of the elevated contour region in Fig. 16(b).

FIG. 15. Diagram depicting the four phases of a propeller rotation through a boundary layer in the propeller BLI configuration. The shaded regions denote the extent of each phase. The critical blade angle, α_δ , is also defined.

18 January 2025 16:12:25

FIG. 16. Phase averaged acoustic results measured from the parallel array, (a) reports results of the $\theta = 90^\circ$ microphone for the three trips. The highlighted segments denote the portions of the rotation where the blade is immersed in the boundary layer. Phased directivity contours are presented for the three trips, (b), (c), and (d), respectively.

The width of the hump in Fig. 16(b) is seen to remain fairly consistent at observer angles $\theta > 90^\circ$. At upstream angles, however, $\theta < 90^\circ$, the broadband noise emissions present minimal increases, as expected from the previous results in Sec. IV B. The directivity contours for Trips B and C, seen in Figs. 16(c) and 16(d), show similar behavior but with stronger levels of broadband noise, even at directivity and blade angles where noise is at a minimum. Trip C presents a widening of the hump, inferring that the broadband turbulence ingestion noise generated during boundary layer immersion is efficiently propagated downstream during the entire immersion phase (i.e., $-\alpha_\delta < \alpha < \alpha_\delta$). It should be noted that the peak location is not influenced by any measurable systematic delay between the encoder and the microphone signals, as otherwise, the peak location would be seen to vary with RPM, which was not observed during testing. The asymmetrical nature of the SPL humps and that the hump peaks do not align with the perpendicular $\alpha = 0^\circ$ position are not entirely unexpected as the blades experience varying inflow angles and steady and unsteady pressure fields between the approach and the retreating phases of rotation.

Further insights into the phased acoustic results, and blade-boundary-layer interaction, may be obtained through applying the

same phase-averaging technique to the velocity field measurements. Here, the velocity measurements taken at $x = -0.06R$ directly upstream of the propeller for the three trips, refer to Sec. III B, are phase averaged. Observing the flow characteristics as the blade passes through the measured location will provide insight into the behavior of the blade-boundary-layer interaction during the blade passage and inform any correlated observations on the far-field noise. The measured profile spans from the plate surface to $y/R = 0.4$, presenting the behavior from within the boundary layer and tip gap, to outside of the boundary layer, except in the case of Trip C. Here, the boundary layer thickness slightly exceeds $y/R = 0.4$, and thus, for this trip, only results within the boundary layer are presented.

Figures 17(a)–17(c) show the phase-averaged mean velocity profiles for each integer blade angle throughout a half rotation, or one blade pass, for Trips A, B, and C, respectively. The velocity envelope is visualized by the gray region and highlighted lines denote the profiles at key or transitional moments in the velocity oscillation. Figures 17(d)–17(f) show the same results in the form of a contour, with the horizontal axis representing blade angle (α). Recall that blade angle values of $\alpha = \pm 90^\circ$ denote the position where the propeller is parallel to the plate, with

FIG. 17. Phase-averaged mean velocity measurements for the three boundary layers at the $x = -0.06R$ position presented as lines (a)–(c) and contours (d)–(f). The left-hand vertical axes are normalized by respective boundary layer thickness (δ), see Table II, and the right-hand axes are consistent with the r/R scale.

no boundary layer immersion, and $\alpha = 0^\circ$ refers to the perpendicular position, i.e., the position of maximum boundary layer interaction, see Fig. 15. The initial state of non-ingestion ($\alpha = \pm 90^\circ$), and the peak ingestion ($\alpha = 0^\circ$) are highlighted and labeled as the dashed black lines in each of Figs. 17(a)–17(c). The boundary layer thickness is denoted by “BL Line,” and the blade tip location is denoted by “Tip Line.” Focusing initially on Trip A, Fig. 17(a), as the blade approaches the plate (from $\alpha = -90^\circ$ to 0°), a steady decrease in velocity is observed until approximately $\alpha = -20^\circ$ where a sharp and significant reduction in local velocity is seen to begin, eventually achieving a minimum of $u_{\text{mean}}/U_\infty \approx 0.62$ at $y/\delta = 3.5$, when the blade reaches $\alpha = -16^\circ$. The subsequent 10° of rotation results in a strong acceleration of flow, beginning first at the $r/R = 0.4$ location and progressing along the full length of the measurement toward the plate as the blade rotates into the perpendicular position. The corresponding contour plot in Fig. 17(d) makes clear this response further from the plate by the slight left-leaning acceleration region at $-16^\circ < \alpha < 0^\circ$. The acceleration results in a peak velocity of $u_{\text{mean}}/U_\infty = 1.33$ at $\alpha = -7^\circ$, occurring very near the boundary layer thickness ($y/\delta = 1$), before a gradual return to the profile of the initial non-ingestion phase at $\alpha = 90^\circ$.

Observing the differences between the phased mean velocity profiles for Trips A, B, and C, in Figs. 17(a)–17(c), respectively, the influence of the boundary layer thickness on the pulsation of the flow due to the blade passage is clear. The regions where the boundary layer is

present ($y/\delta < 1$) are seen to suppress the flow acceleration in all trips, leading to the peak velocities for Trips B and C to occur further away from the plate than that of Trip A. Additionally, a general reduction in peak velocity is observed along the full measurement profile in the case of Trip C. A closer examination reveals that the vertical locations of the peak velocity for Trips A and B coincide well with their respective boundary layer thicknesses. In contrast, in the case of Trip C, the peak velocity is located at approximately $r/R = 0.75$, which is a region of the blade that, in the case of a typical propeller, would experience the most significant loading.⁵¹

Therefore, comparing the results from all three boundary layers, it can be inferred that the velocity behavior is heavily influenced by the presence of the boundary layer, with the resultant velocity profile incorporating the contributions of the propeller blade loading, and that induced by the interaction with the boundary layer. In other words, in the cases of Trips A and B, the maximum velocity is observed to be near $y/\delta = 1$ due to the overlap of the blade loading distribution and the boundary layer influence; whereas, when the blade is immersed beyond the region of significant blade loading, in the case of Trip C, the peak velocity profile follows that of the blade loading distribution, however, at a reduced magnitude.

The effect of propeller–boundary-layer interaction on the velocity field are better visualized in the contour plots of Figs. 17(d)–17(f), where in Fig. 17(d) the shape of a typical blade loading distribution [see, for instance, Fig. 8(b) in the study by van Arnhem *et al.*⁵¹] is

observed in the contour outside of the boundary layer ($y/\delta > 1$). Comparing this contour shape to that of Trip B and C, shown in Figs. 17(e) and 17(f), it is evident that the interference of the thicker boundary layers causes the profile to be augmented and reduces the time it takes for the flow within the boundary layer to recover from the blade passage.

Correlating these results with the phased SPL, it can be observed that the peak broadband turbulence ingestion noise, as experienced at the measurement location, $\alpha = 0^\circ$, is generated during the peak of the upstream flow acceleration, when the blade is at $\alpha = -5^\circ$. It is important to understand that the current velocity results do not present the inflow variation of a particular blade throughout its rotation, but instead present the effects of the blade passage at the chosen measurement location. The measurement line is positioned at the location of maximum boundary layer immersion, i.e., $\alpha = 0^\circ$. Hence, a peak in RMS or mean velocity here may not correlate with the peak RMS velocity experienced by the blade; however, it is assumed to contain the most significant turbulence content that will interact with the blade, due to its location of maximum immersion, and, hence, result in the generation of maximum turbulence ingestion noise. However, a more definitive correlation between peak blade inflow characteristics and noise could be obtained through the use of phase-averaged on-blade measurements, which is not feasible in the current setup.

Investigating the RMS velocity profiles throughout the rotation, in addition to the phase-averaged mean velocity, can reveal further important characteristics of the propeller-boundary-layer interaction. The velocity RMS can serve as an indication of the level of

turbulence or degree of velocity fluctuation, which is useful when attempting to understand the phased far-field acoustic results in Fig. 16. Figure 18 depicts the phased RMS velocity profiles measured at the $x = -0.06R$ position, just upstream of the rotor disk. Similarly to Fig. 17, Figs. 18(a)–18(c) present the RMS velocity profiles for Trips A, B, and C at every integer blade angle from $-90^\circ \leq \alpha \leq 90^\circ$. Figures 18(d)–18(f), present the same profiles in the form of contour plots with the horizontal axis denoting the blade angle (α). As expected, across all three boundary layers, the non-ingestion blade angles (black lines), beginning at $\alpha = \pm 90^\circ$, exhibit minimal velocity fluctuation. Low RMS velocity levels are maintained well into the approach phase until $\alpha = -17^\circ$, where a strong increase initiates from the $r/R = 0.4$ location and progresses toward the plate as the blade rotates, similar to the behavior observed earlier in the mean velocity profiles in Fig. 17. The slightly diagonal characteristic of the peak RMS region in the contour plots of Figs. 18(d)–18(f) also shows this clearly. The peak level of RMS is observed across all trips to be at blade angle $\alpha = -10^\circ$, where the flow is in the process of being rapidly accelerated, as shown in Fig. 17. The peak velocity RMS blade angle is not seen to vary between trips, which is dissimilar to the behavior of the peak mean velocity where a variation of $\pm 2^\circ$ was observed. Conversely, the magnitude of the peak RMS is seen to be strongly influenced by the boundary layer thickness, where for Trip A, the RMS achieves $u_{rms}/U_\infty = 0.20$ and for Trip C, achieves $u_{rms}/U_\infty = 0.28$, as can be seen in Figs. 18(a) and 18(c), respectively. Additionally, unlike the phased mean velocity profiles, the location of the peak does not

FIG. 18. Phase-averaged velocity RMS measurements for the three boundary layers at the $x = -0.06R$ position, presented as line (a)–(c) and contours (d)–(f). The left-hand vertical axes are normalized by respective boundary layer thickness (δ), see Table II, and the right-hand axes are consistent with the r/R scale.

directly correspond to the boundary layer thickness and instead remains close to the blade tip region ($r/R = 0.9$). This suggests that the source of the peak RMS is directly related to the perturbations of the flow due to the blade passage, in particular, around the blade tip region. Immediately following this peak in RMS, the flow rapidly returns to low $\alpha = \pm 90^\circ$ levels in all three cases.

Outside of the transitional blade angles ($-16^\circ < \alpha < -5^\circ$), there exist notable differences between the boundary layers, as seen by the variations of the RMS profiles at $\alpha \pm 90^\circ$ between Trips A, B, and C in Figs. 18(a)–18(c), where the increased level of boundary layer turbulence is evident when increasing boundary layer thickness. The differences are more clearly observed when comparing Figs. 18(d)–18(f), where the background level of RMS is observed to be more substantial as boundary layer thickness increases. In these contours, it is also possible to observe a second mild increase in RMS at $\alpha = 0$. Referring back to the phased SPL and phased mean velocity results in Figs. 16 and 17, respectively, the peak broadband SPL_α generation was observed to occur at $\alpha = -5^\circ$, with peak phased mean velocity also seen to occur at very similar blade angles. However, peak RMS at the current measurement location was seen to occur at $\alpha = -10^\circ$. Hence, the variations of turbulence ingestion noise emissions over a rotation correlate more closely with that of the peak of the phased mean velocity, rather than the peak of velocity RMS when comparing the peak magnitudes of the phase-averaged velocity and acoustics. Nevertheless, it is worthwhile to mention that the nature of phase-averaged flow effects on the noise generation mechanism of a propeller is a highly complex relationship, as demonstrated in the current study, particularly for non-axisymmetric inflows. The current phase-averaged results are not able to provide a complete understanding of the correlation between velocity and acoustic fields in each phase of the blade rotation, and instead, help highlight key areas that would benefit from further investigation using additional experimental or numerical techniques to identify the underlying physical mechanisms involved.

VI. CONCLUSION

The present study experimentally investigated the acoustic and aerodynamic characteristics of a propeller ingesting various turbulent boundary layers. Three boundary layers of different thicknesses and turbulence levels were generated using different tripping devices. To examine the effect of boundary layer ingestion on the radiated noise of the propeller, both far-field acoustics and the flow field upstream of the propeller were experimentally measured with two microphone arrays and hot-wire anemometry, respectively. Additionally, an angular encoder was used to track the phase angle of the propeller rotation and hence allowing the analyses of phase-averaged results.

The effect of the propeller on the upstream boundary layer profiles was first examined, where it was found that the propeller induced a general increase in the mean velocity in the incoming boundary layer, notably modifying the profile shape at the studied advance ratio, due to the flow acceleration induced by the propeller. Similarly, a significant increase in the velocity fluctuations was also observed. However, once contributions of the BPF and its harmonics were filtered from the velocity signal, it was shown that the propeller induced limited variations to the turbulence content of the incoming boundary layer. The turbulence length scale analysis showed clear and significant increases in eddy size between the trips throughout the boundary layer thickness, but again, showed that the presence of the propeller only marginally affected the turbulence length scales of the inflow. The

turbulence contents and length scale results demonstrated an overall absence of notable inflow distortion and eddy stretching for the present propeller operating condition (advance ratio of 0.91), agreeing well with previous studies.

The far-field noise results showed clear variations in both the frequency-dependent acoustic spectra and the OASPL directivity when increasing the boundary layer thickness and turbulence contents. Substantial increases in the broadband components were evident at downstream observer angles along the microphone array parallel to the plate, while at upstream observer angles, such an increase is significantly less apparent. Conversely, increases in the tones were more noticeable in the microphone array orthogonal to the plate and, in this case, the directivity is biased upstream. The OASPL directivity results showed the maximum difference between Trip A and Trip C was 7.7 dB at the most downstream microphone in the parallel array. The differences in the acoustic spectra and directivity highlight that the noise emission and propagation of the present BLI configuration is highly directional, and is largely propagated along the blade normals. Thus, by careful consideration of the blade normal vector orientation during blade–boundary layer interaction, it is possible to direct the broadband BLI noise emissions as desired, providing a useful avenue for BLI noise directivity optimization during aircraft design. Inferring from both the acoustic and the flow field results, the increases in tonal and broadband noise are therefore most likely attributed to the elevated turbulence contents of the boundary layers themselves rather than the effect of propeller inflow distortion for the present BLI conditions.

Phase-averaged analyses of both the far-field acoustics and velocity measurements revealed the variations of the broadband noise generation over a blade revolution. It was found that the peak noise generation, as measured parallel to the plate, occurred at $\alpha = -5^\circ$, close to when the propeller is perpendicular to the plate where the most significant boundary layer ingestion takes place. This peak location did not vary significantly between trips; however, the peak noise magnitude differed by approximately 14 dB between Trip A and Trip C, and the breadth of the increased noise period widened for thicker boundary layers, corroborating the fact that the higher turbulence contents from the boundary layer would lead to greater noise emission in the BLI configuration. The phased velocity showed peak upstream velocity also occurred in the region of $\alpha = -5^\circ$, while the peak acceleration occurred near $\alpha = -10^\circ$. Future insights may be obtained through the use of phase-averaged, on-blade measurements.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

I. Zaman: Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Methodology (equal); Validation (equal); Visualization (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **M. Falsi:** Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal). **B. Zang:** Conceptualization (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Supervision (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **M. Azarpeyvand:** Conceptualization (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Methodology (equal); Project administration (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **S. Meloni:** Formal analysis (equal); Methodology (equal); Supervision (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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